

Using Game-Based Learning to Enhance Student Engagement in Multivariate Calculus for Engineering Students

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Abstract

This study explores the potential of game-based learning (GBL) to improve engagement in Multivariate Calculus (MC) among first-year Aerospace Engineering students. Traditional approaches to calculus education often struggle to sustain student interest, especially within diverse, international classrooms. To address this challenge, a modified board game based on "Snakes and Ladders" was developed and integrated into a core mathematics course. Structured classroom observations and post-intervention surveys provide insight into cognitive, behavioral, emotional and social engagement. Initial findings suggest that GBL can effectively foster metacognitive engagement in STEM education, providing a promising direction for improving abstract mathematical learning.

Introduction

Calculus, often perceived as abstract and challenging, presents significant engagement difficulties for first-year engineering students with diverse educational backgrounds. Traditional teaching methods (teacher-led learning) used during guided self-study activities - where instructors dominate, and students take passive roles - do not positively impact students' behavioural and emotional engagement (see Lim (2023)). To address these issues, this project will implement GBL in the Multivariate Calculus course for first-year Aerospace Engineering students. This course, taught annually in the third quarter, runs from February to March and the students use the book by Adams (2021) which is widely used at Dutch universities for Calculus.

Based on the above considerations and the need in examining the impact of a game-based intervention on student engagement, this study aims to investigate the following research question: *"What is the observed effect of implementing a board game, designed by GBL, in a course of Multivariate Calculus on engagement levels of first-year Aerospace Engineering students?"*

Background

Multivariate Calculus is one of the crucial mathematics service courses like Calculus and Linear Algebra, for the students to have the ability to apply sophisticated mathematical calculations and concepts alongside physical understanding. Despite its importance, the course's abstract nature frequently challenges students, impacting their engagement and retention. Pepper et al. (2012) identify common student difficulties in upper division electricity and magnetism course, which rely on vector calculus pre-knowledge. They highlight a specific challenge: students often fail to select appropriate mathematical tools

for problem-solving, a process that crucially involves ‘*decision-making*’ skills. Furthermore, as was emphasized by Craig (2022), observations during the Corona pandemic show that decision-making skills are critical not only in open-book assessments but also in closed-book scenarios, which demand *higher-order cognitive skills* and a deep *conceptual understanding*.

Engaging in game play promotes *metacognitive skills* and an understanding of the interconnections between concepts, offering diverse perspectives. It improves the learning process by helping students to visually structure new information and actively engage in their own learning process (Kustusch (2014)). Research by Anagnostopoulou (2023) supports GBL as a valid and effective contemporary method to enhance students’ *engagement and motivation*.

Through the implementation of the below-mentioned intervention, we aim to investigate how participation in a game designed by GBL principles can enhance student engagement and motivation, as well as improve effective decision-making skills, thereby potentially addressing the noted challenges in Multivariate Calculus.

Intervention Design

The traditional board game "Snakes & Ladders", which can be seen in Figure 1, has been used and adapted into an interactive learning tool to enhance students' engagement with course material. In this version, the game board features numbered squares and players progress by rolling dice, aiming to be the first to finish. The game includes "ladders," which advance players towards the end, and "snakes," which send them back towards the start.

Figure 1. Board Game Layout.

A key modification is the introduction of educational challenges: when landing on a square, players draw a card from one of six categories based on course content and answer the question on the card. Other players evaluate the answers. The question cards that team members hesitate to answer are collected by the teacher. These topics are then addressed during the discussion following the game session. The game concludes when a player reaches the final square or when allotted time expires, with the furthest advanced player declared the winner.

There are four types of cards: *True\False Cards*, *Decision Tree Cards*, *Keyword Cards* and *Power Cards*. Both *True\False Cards* and *Decision Tree Cards* pose a question that tests the player's knowledge/understanding. The optional decision tree diagram for hint is provided during the game. The *Power Card* is a rare bonus and not easily earned. This card allows you to *either* skip a snake (avoiding being sent back) *or* keep your place even if you answer incorrectly on your next turn. You decide when to use it for maximum advantage. The *Power Card* is inspired by the **Core Drive 6: scarcity** from the *Octalysis Gamification Framework* (see Chou (2019)), adding excitement and strategic depth to the game. The *Keyword card* challenges players to connect key concepts from the course material. Each card presents a main keyword related to the course topics. The player's task is to provide 2–3 supporting keywords related to the main keyword and explain their connections.

Before the game, a reflection game activity is introduced during one of the lectures to engage students in active learning and allow them to contribute by designing some of the Keyword Cards. This activity not only gives students additional practice with the course material but also supports **Core Drive 4: Ownership** from the *Octalysis Gamification Framework*.

Methodology

This study was conducted as a pilot using a qualitative exploratory approach to examine the impact of a board game, designed with Game-Based Learning (GBL) principles, on student engagement in Multivariate Calculus. The intervention was implemented during the final session of the course with approximately 30 first-year Aerospace Engineering students, including Dutch, international and HBO bridging students. The redesigned “Snakes & Ladders” game was integrated with core Multivariate Calculus topics, aiming to foster active learning through structured gameplay and peer interaction.

The qualitative data obtained from observations during the game were used to clarify, explicate and enhance the findings from the exploratory quantitative data collected through questionnaires (Hamari (2016); Wang (2016)). The students completed a post-intervention survey consisting of both closed items using Likert scales, to assess cognitive, behavioural, emotional and social engagement, and open-ended questions about the game experience. While this phase focused on qualitative insights, a mixed-method follow-up is planned for a later stage. This will involve a larger dataset, pre- and post-intervention surveys and semi-structured interviews to assess changes in engagement and further explore the educational impact of the intervention over time.

Conclusion

This pilot study demonstrates the promising potential of game-based learning to enhance engagement in abstract mathematics courses such as Multivariate Calculus. By integrating a redesigned “Snakes & Ladders” board game into the curriculum, students were encouraged to participate actively, reflect on key concepts and engage in collaborative decision-making. Initial results suggest improvements across multiple dimensions of engagement, particularly in fostering metacognitive and social learning experiences. While the current findings are based on qualitative data from surveys and observations, the next phase will extend the research through a mixed-method design to include larger cohorts and longitudinal data. During our presentation at the SEFI Special Interest Group in Mathematics Seminar, we will share further insights, including the outcomes of follow-up interviews, to offer a more comprehensive understanding of how game-based activities can support deeper learning and sustained motivation in STEM education.

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